

ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES (ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE) AND EMPLOYEES' WORK EFFICIENCY IN SELECTED POLYTECHNICS IN SOUTHWEST NIGERIA

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Article Info

Keywords: Employees, Organizational Culture, Polytechnic, Work Efficiency.

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.17084932

Abstract

This study examined the effect of organizational culture on employees' work efficiency in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria. Data were sourced through a questionnaire, and 480 questionnaires were distributed, while 436 questionnaires were returned and analyzed. The regression analysis revealed that organizational culture significantly and positively impacts work efficiency, with a coefficient of 0.501, indicating that a one-unit increase in organizational culture leads to a 0.501 unit improvement in work efficiency. The t-statistic (15.341) and a highly significant p-value (0.000) confirm the statistical significance of this relationship. The model explains 35.2% of the variation in work efficiency ($R^2 = 0.352$, $F(1,434) = 235.354$, $p = 0.000$). The findings align with the contingency theory, which underscores the importance of adapting management practices to specific organizational needs. The study highlighted the critical processes of culture realignment as essential for achieving successful change outcomes. The study concludes that while organizational culture significantly enhances work efficiency, its impact is relatively modest. Consequently, it is recommended that management in the selected polytechnics prioritize promoting an inclusive and diverse work environment, fostering constructive feedback, and supporting a healthy work-life balance to amplify the positive effects of organizational culture on work performance.

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century organization, human elements are required to initiate and drive activities toward achieving set goals. To this end, these employees become key assets to the organization in enhancing and sustaining performance. This, to a great extent, shows how employee performance is critical to any organization's success

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or failure, particularly in a changing workplace. The business environment is challenging because of the intense rivalry between companies, especially regarding who has the largest market share. The corporate environment is increasingly dynamic and complex because of intense competition. However, the education industry is not left behind because it is currently facing intense competition at both the domestic and global levels.

In recent years, academic scholars and corporate practitioners have researched employee work efficiency as an engaging theme (Bouckennooghe et al., 2021; Muftahu & Jamil, 2021). Despite many studies on the above assertion, recent empirical studies have revealed a continuous reduction in the work performance of employees worldwide (Rocheville, Keys, & Bartunek, 2021). Previous studies have suggested that this could be attributable to some factors that revolve around the manner in which changes in organizations are being managed (Beniflah & Veloz, 2021; Bellantuono et al., 2021). Decreased levels of performance in the organization are categorized as below-standard employee performance, absenteeism, delayed process, and loss of revenue. Issues such as poor employee creativity, work inefficiency, declining work quality, and low commitment are also considered symptoms of declining employee performance (Rocheville et al., 2021). Given the dynamism in the higher education system, the status quo must change if the sector thrives to meet the 2030 SDGs on education. The 2030 SDG on education is a call to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote opportunities for lifelong learning for all. As part of its constituents, it also provides access to affordable and quality technical, vocational, and tertiary education (Bellantuono et al., 2021).

One of the significant challenges facing developing nations, including Nigeria, is the effective management of employee efficiency to ensure organizational growth. Organizational culture plays a critical role in shaping employees' efficiency and productivity. Culture, as a product of human creation, provides a framework for societal and organizational behavior. As Fahmi (2016) posited, when firmly established, cultural systems influence the patterns of life within societies and organizations. Change remains prevalent in every organization, and the speed at which it occurs is alarming, especially with the advent of the Internet and the deployment of new technologies. This led to new normal, forcing organizations to adapt their modes of operation to align with current realities (Stoneham et al., 2021). Organizational change is complex by nature, and this makes it difficult to handle because of the uncertainty it creates in the minds of the employees. Nonetheless, when organizational change is well planned and implemented, it engenders many tangible benefits, including improved competitiveness, improved financial performance, and better customer service delivery, as well as improved employee satisfaction. Change is crucial for organizational survival and growth, and employees play a leading role in achieving change initiatives. Continuous change and adaptation are necessary for organizations to remain competitive (Stoneham et al., 2021; Hofmann & Vermunt, 2021).

Organizational change occurs in different ways, including downsizing, merger and acquisition, joint ventures, new leadership, technology implementation, and changes in goals or regulations. For instance, the effect of an organization's downsizing by laying off some workers could result in dissatisfaction among other employees. Similarly, downsizing could create economic and psychological problems for workers who survive the layoffs. This is because those who survived the downsizing would experience some difficult situations, including work overload, which ultimately often results in frustration, dissatisfaction, and stress, hence the need for change management (Lott & Booth-LeDoux, 2021). Organization culture covers a systematic strategy for dealing with the transition or transformation of corporate goals. Organizational culture is a habit that lasts a long time and is used and applied in life work activities as one of the drivers for improving employees' and company managers' quality of work (Lott & Booth-LeDoux, 2021).

Employees' role in the polytechnic system is recognized as crucial in achieving the overall goal and quality of polytechnic education. However, polytechnics can rarely deliver on their mandates of producing resourceful graduates without adequate employee work performance. The challenge of employee work efficiency has become a significant concern among stakeholders in Nigeria's polytechnics. This is because it has far-reaching repercussions on overall institutional performance. The management of these institutions expresses significant concerns over their employees' work efficiency. Educational institutions of this nature assume a crucial role in building a nation's manpower by fostering technical and vocational proficiencies, rendering their personnel's competence a vital determinant of their efficacy. Specifically, the creative potential of employees in Nigerian Polytechnics is affected by a range of workplace problems (Xiong et al., 2021). The educational system's inflexible and bureaucratic structure, combined with restricted avenues for imaginative thought, frequently impedes individuals from manifesting their creative abilities (Ghavifekr & Fung, 2021).

Furthermore, the level of job efficiency plays a crucial role in determining an employee's overall work performance. Nevertheless, employees within Nigerian Polytechnics encounter many obstacles that weaken their overall effectiveness (Ahmad et al., 2021). Challenges such as obsolete infrastructure, insufficient resources, and bureaucratic procedures not only hinder productivity but also contribute to employee dissatisfaction and exhaustion. The absence of streamlined and efficient work processes harms both the quality of education offered and the morale of employees. The scope of this research was limited to investigating the influence of organizational culture on the work efficiency of employees in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Efficiency

The term 'employee efficiency' describes the processes and resources that an organization uses to produce the highest quality products or services as efficiently as possible. Operations can be defined as jobs or tasks consisting of one or more elements or subtasks, typically performed in one location. Operations transform resource or data inputs into desired goods, services, or results and create and deliver value to customers. The term 'efficiency' is viewed in both the industrial organization and strategic management literature as the product of firm-specific factors, such as management skills, innovation, cost control, and market share, as determinants of current firm performance and stability (Blumberg et al., 2019).

Operational efficiency refers to an organization's capability to deliver products or services to its customers in the most cost-effective manner possible while still ensuring the high quality of its products, service, and support¹⁵. Operational efficiency refers to an organization's capabilities and performance. The scholar further describes it as an organization's ability to minimize input waste and maximize resource utilization to deliver quality, cheaper products and services to their customers. It is a useful measure for managing available resources (Hee & Shanmugam, 2019; Paliwal & Raskar, 2019).

Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is a system of shared assumptions, values, and beliefs that dictate how an organization interacts with its internal and external environments (Akpa, Asikhia, & Nneji, 2021). These shared values significantly influence employees' behaviors and attitudes, shaping their interactions and decision-making processes (Schein, 2010). Organizational culture includes deeply held assumptions, norms, and values that guide interpretation and action, defining appropriate behaviors for different situations (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). When these assumptions are collectively embraced, a corporate culture that influences employee identification with the organization is established (Kotter & Heskett, 1992). Some scholars argue that

organizational culture encompasses various social elements, such as dress codes, language, symbols of authority, myths, and rituals, which contribute to defining an organization's character and norms (Trice & Beyer, 1993). Others have limited their conceptualization of organizational culture to core elements such as beliefs, behaviors, and attitudes, emphasizing its fundamental role in organizational functioning (Schein, 2010). The impact of organizational culture extends to competition and performance by shaping employee engagement, motivation, and strategic direction. A well-defined organizational culture serves as a strategic asset, shaping internal structures, systems, and leadership styles (Mohammed, Firmansyah & Djudiyah, 2024; Alateeg & Alhammadi, 2024, Schein, 2010; Tadesse Bogale & Debela, 2024).). It influences how employees interact, make decisions, and align with the company's mission and vision (Alateeg & Alhammadi, 2024).Furthermore, organizational culture fosters an environment conducive to innovation, enabling firms to develop strategic agility and maintain competitive advantage (Egunjobi & Aremu., 2023). Research has shown that organizations with strong cultures outperform those with weaker ones, as cohesive cultures drive financial success, employee satisfaction, and long-term sustainability (Hofstede, 2001; Ghaleb, 2024).

THEORETICAL REVIEW

This study is underpinned by the Contingency Theory. In 1964, Fiedler propounded the contingency theory (CT). CT was built on the premise that some exigencies influence the organization's performance beyond the organization. This means that when an organization can fit itself with contingent factors (e.g., culture, strategy, technology, structure, and environment), such alignment will guarantee improved performance. The fundamental assumption of CT is that it considers every organization an open system, one that can influence and be influenced by the external environment. Hence, the different ways in which organizations are planned are highlighted. The bottom line here is that success is based on how well an organization fits its contingencies. The whole organizational-contingence fit is a chain of activities that evolves because the business environment is dynamic (Narayanan & Adams, 2017).

However, scholars have criticized the CT assumptions. First, some scholars suggested that the desire to accomplish internal and external alignment remains an obscure objective, especially for firms that operate within an environment with several conflicting demands and for firms with internal organization trade-offs and high-performance targets (Skogland & Hansen, 2017). Accordingly, some scholars argued that it is exceptionally challenging to conceptualize a theoretical answer in a scenario like this is exceptionally challenging. Furthermore, there were the configuration theorists. They believed that it is not practicable for firms to align entirely with their contingencies, considering that the factors themselves continue to change as the firm adapts its structure to fit the contingent factors. In the end, the fit issue does not materialize. They further argued that CT is not proactive; instead, it is reactive because it outlines what managers can do when faced with individual circumstances. Even at that, CT fails to specify precisely what these managers should do under these different situations.

In a study conducted by scholars, CT was supported by providing empirical evidence to substantiate how structure influences organizational performance. The results indicated that the appropriateness of the organizational structure lead to operational efficiency (AlManei et al., 2018). To further support the CT, some scholars have studied the performance effect of strategic management. Their study repeated the contingency perspective narrative that there is no one best way to manage an organization. Specifically, managerial and strategic choices are context-specific. Furthermore, Titus and Anderson (2018) used CT to support the attention-based view to provide a more robust theoretical framework to underpin their study (AlManei et al., 2018; Rosenbaum et al., 2018).

REVIEW OF EMPIRICAL STUDIES

Before the study on organizational culture and work efficiency of employees, several studies have examined organizational culture with inconsistent results. For example, the investigation into the role of change management on employees' performance in the agricultural sector found that proper communication of new policies and work procedures increases employees' productivity as it makes them work faster. Proper communication increases the chances of employees adapting to changes and accomplishing tasks on a faster scale. In this vein, Errida and Lotfi (2020) found that change communication is a major determinant of workforce task accomplishment. However, an employee's skills level causes task accomplishment rather than communication. No matter how well employees are oriented about intended changes in an organization, if the employees do not have high skill levels, they will not be able to accomplish tasks on time as well as involvement. The need to fully involve employees during organizational change cannot be overemphasized. When management succeeds in involving employees in the formulation and implementation of organizational changes, the employees gain a better understanding of the changes; they find it very easy to adapt to changes, which also encourages high levels of innovativeness. Employee involvement during organizational changes makes it possible for employees to assimilate new ideas and practices and also brings out the best possible innovativeness in the employees (Errida & Lotfi, 2020).

Similarly, a scholar maintained that for organizational changes to be effective, management must endeavor to get the staff involved and adequately informed at every stage right from the beginning. He also pointed out that a high level of employee involvement during changes implies that employees will have a better understanding of the changes and will become more innovative. In a related study, a researcher investigated the impact of an open system on employees' productivity and found that employees who are actively involved in the organizational change process are more innovative and productive than their counterparts who were not involved (Todnem, 2020). However, a scholar is of the view that experience rather than involvement causes employees' innovativeness during organizational changes.

A researcher conducted an analysis of the management of change processes in the Civil Service of Lesotho (Asikhia et al., 2021). This study used a qualitative method and a case study design. An objective was to determine the forces of organizational change in the civil service. A sample size of 50 was used. The study concluded that the driving forces for change in Lesotho's civil service were both internal and external. Some external forces that caused change initiatives in the Civil Service are new government regulations and technological changes that affect work. The internal forces include human resources problems regarding the availability of qualified personnel and managerial decisions to introduce systems to solve problems such as inadequate reward systems and poor performance of the organization.

A scholar at the Ejisu Government Hospital conducted research on change as a tool for enhancing organizational development (Aitken & Von-Treuer, 2021). The objective was to determine the various sources of resistance to organizational change at the hospital. The study used a quantitative method and a case study and exploratory design. This study used a sample size of 59. The study revealed that the primary sources of resistance to change were blind, intellectual (ideological), and political resistance. Many factors on the personal level underlying these resistances were isolated, of which poor communication was identified as the major reason why people resisted change at the hospital. In addition, a study was conducted on resistance to change in Indian, Chinese, and Estonian organizations. The authors interviewed 177 business consultants and managers who had participated in change management projects in India, China, and Estonia. Quantitative and qualitative methods were used to analyze the impact of national culture on change management. The cause of resistance

was found to be mainly fear in Indian and Estonian organizations, but inertia in Chinese organizations. Increased stress was the most frequently experienced negative factor during change management projects in all three countries. Stress was caused by leadership problems in India and increased workload in Estonia.

A scholar conducted a study on organizational change capacity (OCC) and organizational performance in China (Harrison et al., 2021). A series of 130 qualified employees in a knowledge-based organization were questioned to test the hypothesis. The measurement tool was a two-part questionnaire (organizational change capacity and performance). The validity of the questionnaire was ascertained by experts, specialists, and professors of management based on the face validity method. Using the results of the pretest, Cronbach's test showed very high reliability. The results of the regression analysis showed that the regression line ascribes changes in the dependent variable (performance) to the independent variable (organizational change capacity). This means that a high percentage of change in OP (77.3%) will be explainable and predictable with OCC. Overall, the results of this study showed a significant, positive, and strong relationship between OCC and OP.

A scholar researched the impact of organizational change on employee performance in the banking sector of Pakistan. Questionnaires were used for collecting primary data. The variables considered for change in the study were leadership, communication, procedural justice, employee development, and tolerance to change. The study sample size was 252; therefore, descriptive statistics and correlation analysis techniques were used for data analysis in the SPSS software. The results showed that organizational change has a significant positive impact on employee performance in Pakistan's banking sector.

However, while some studies concluded that change management practices can lead to improved job satisfaction and reduced employee stress, others report mixed or negative effects. The divergence here often relates to how the change is implemented, the change, and employee differences. Some employees may perceive change as an opportunity for growth, whereas others may perceive it as a threat to their job security, leading to increased stress and decreased job satisfaction. In addition, the effectiveness of change management practices and their impact on employee performance can vary significantly across cultural contexts. While participative and inclusive change management practices may be highly effective in cultures that value individualism and low power distance, such practices may not be as effective in cultures with high power distance and collectivism (Kharbat & AlSoud, 2019; Paramitha et al., 2020). This divergence highlights the importance of tailoring change management practices to fit the organizational cultural context.

Moreover, the literature diverges regarding the long-term versus short-term effects of change management on employee performance. Some studies suggest that while change initiatives may lead to short-term improvements in performance, these effects may not be sustainable over the long term without ongoing support and reinforcement (Sulistiyani et al., 2020). This discrepancy highlights the need for continuous evaluation and adjustment of change management practices to maintain and improve employee performance over time. The empirical review of recent studies on the link between organizational change management practices and employee job performance highlights convergence and divergence. Effective change management can positively impact employee performance, with key factors in this process being leadership, communication, participation, and training. However, the impact of change on employee stress and job satisfaction, the influence of cultural context, and the sustainability of performance improvements over time remain areas of divergence. Future research should focus on longitudinal studies that examine the long-term effects of change management practices on employee performance and comparative studies that explore the effectiveness of these practices across different cultural contexts to bridge these gaps. Additionally, organizations should consider adopting a more holistic and adaptive approach to change management that addresses their workforce's diverse needs and

perspectives, ensuring that change initiatives lead to sustainable performance improvements (Balluck et al., 2020).

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of this study comprised all the staff of the Polytechnics in Southwest; hence, the target population is eight thousand six hundred and six (8,606) staff of the selected Polytechnics in Southwest. The selected institutions include two (2) polytechnics (one federal and one state-owned) per state. Hence, this totals twelve (12) polytechnics given that the Southwest of Nigeria comprises Lagos, Ogun, Ekiti, Osun, Ondo, and Oyo States. In determining the sample size for the study, the Cochran formula was used.

$$n = \frac{NZ^2pq}{d^2(N-1) + Z^2pq}$$

Where:-

n = sample size, N = population size (total number of staff), Z = 95% confidence interval (Z = 1.96); p = 0.5
0.9604; q = 1-p; d = degree of estimation (0.05);

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{8606 \times (1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times (1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2 \times (8606-1) + (1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times (1-0.5)} \\ &= \frac{8,265.2024}{20.660605} \end{aligned}$$

$$n = 400.046 \sim 400$$

However, to compensate for the non-response probability, 20% of the sample size was added to increase the sample base, as suggested by Khan and Iqbal (2020). 20% for anticipated non-response (0.2 x 400) is equal to 80. Therefore, n = 400 + 80 = 480 participants from selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria.

In collecting data from the employees of selected polytechnics structured closed-ended questionnaire divided into 2 sections namely, Section A and B was used. Section A covered the socio-demographic variables with seven (7) items; section B covered organizational culture on work efficiency with twelve (12) items. In line with the existing literature, the response options provided in this study's questionnaire follow the 4-point Likert-type scale. This is an ordinal interval scale numbered from 4 to 1. The response options in the questionnaire were as follows: 4 = strongly agree; 3 = agree; 2 = disagree; 1 = strongly disagree.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Data Presentation

A total of 480 copies of the questionnaire were administered, and four hundred and sixty-six (466) copies were returned. After sorting the questionnaires only four hundred and thirty-six (436) copies were certified as duly filled and considered usable. The useable questionnaire had a response rate of 90.83%.

Demographic Data Presentation**Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents**

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	196	45.0%
	Female	240	55.0%
Age	21-30 years	102	23.4%
	31-40 years	226	51.8%
	41-50 years	57	13.1%
	51-60 years	45	10.3%
	61-65 years	6	1.4%
Education	ND/NCE	20	4.6%
	BSc/HND	331	75.9%
	Masters	73	16.7%
	PhD	12	2.8%
Marital Status	Single	135	31.0%
	Married	292	67.0%
	Divorced	6	1.4%
	Separated	3	0.7%
Ethnicity	Yoruba	374	85.8%
	Hausa	12	2.8%
	Igbo	39	8.9%
	Others	11	2.5%
Length of the Service	Below 5years	93	21.3%
	6-10 years	238	54.6%
	11-15 years	57	13.1%
	16-20 years	42	9.6%
	20years+	6	1.4%
Nature of the job	Teaching	277	63.5%
	Non-teaching	159	36.5%

Source: Field Survey Results (2024)

Table 1 presents the demographic and personal profiles of the respondents. According to the demographic and personal profile of respondents, as shown in Table 4.2, 196 respondents representing 45.0% were male, while 240 respondents representing 55.0% were female, indicating that most of the respondents were female. Also, 102 respondents representing 23.4% were between 21-30years, 226 respondents representing 51.8% were 31-40years, 57 respondents representing 13.1% were 41-50years, 45 respondents representing 10.3% were 51-60years, and 6 respondents representing 1.4% were 61-65years. Furthermore, 20 respondents (4.6%) had an ND/NCE, 331 respondents representing 75.9% had BSc/HND, 73 respondents (16.7%) had a Masters, and 12 respondents (2.8%) had a PhD. In addition, 135 respondents (31.0%) were single, 292 (67.0%) were married, 6 (1.4%) were divorced, and 3 (0.7%) were separated. Meanwhile, 374 respondents representing 85.8% were Yoruba, 12 respondents representing 2.8% were Hausa, 39 respondents representing 8.9% were Igbo, and 11 respondents representing 2.5% were others. Moreover, 93 respondents (21.3% had below 5years length of

service, 238 respondents representing 54.6% had 6-10years, 57 respondents representing 13.1% had 11-15years, 42 respondents representing 9.6% had 16-20years, and 6 respondents representing 1.4% had 20years+. Additionally, 277 respondents representing 63.5% were teaching staff, while 159 respondents representing 36.5% were non-teaching staff.

Analysis of the Responses

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis of Employees' Organization Culture and Work Efficiency in Selected Polytechnics in Southwest, Nigeria

Effect of Organizational Culture on Work Efficiency	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
My organization actively promotes an inclusive and diverse work culture.	139 (31.9%)	279 (64.0%)	18 (4.1%)	-	3.28
The values of my organization align well with my personal values.	217 (49.8%)	187 (42.9%)	29 (6.7%)	3 (0.7%)	3.42
My organization effectively adapts to new challenges and environmental changes	144 (33.0%)	234 (53.7%)	58 (13.3%)	-	3.20
Employees are actively engaged in contributing to the organizational culture	208 (47.7%)	162 (37.2%)	33 (7.6%)	33 (7.6%)	3.25
There is a strong culture of providing constructive feedback within my organization.	167 (38.3%)	243 (55.7%)	20 (4.6%)	6 (1.4%)	3.31
My organization supports a healthy work-life balance for its employees.	194 (44.5%)	209 (47.9%)	30 (6.9%)	3 (0.7%)	3.36
I consistently complete my tasks within the allotted time frame.	149 (34.2%)	234 (53.7%)	21 (4.8%)	32 (7.3%)	3.15
I effectively prioritize my tasks to maximize my productivity.	187 (42.9%)	203 (46.6%)	37 (8.5%)	9 (2.1%)	3.30
I regularly review and optimize my work processes to improve efficiency.	174 (39.9%)	256 (58.7%)	6 (1.4%)	-	3.39
I can simultaneously manage multiple tasks without compromising on quality	172 (39.4%)	223 (51.1%)	35 (8.0%)	6 (1.4%)	3.29
I effectively use the resources available to me to enhance work efficiency	231 (53.0%)	187 (42.9%)	18 (4.1%)	-	3.49
I quickly adapt to new tools and technologies that can improve my work efficiency.	203 (46.6%)	218 (50.0%)	15 (3.4%)	-	3.43
Weighted Mean					3.32

Decision rule 1.00–1.49 = very low, 1.50–2.49 = low, 2.50–3.49 = high, 3.50-4.00= very high. Note: SA: strongly agree, A: agree, D: disagree, SD: strongly disagree

Source: Field Survey Results (2024)

The results indicate generally positive perceptions of organizational culture and its impact on WEE in the surveyed institutions, with an overall weighted mean of 3.32. A significant majority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that their organizations promote an inclusive and diverse work culture (95.9%, mean = 3.28),

align organizational values with personal values (92.7%, mean = 3.42), and adapt effectively to new challenges (86.7%, mean = 3.20). Employee engagement in contributing to organizational culture is widely acknowledged (84.9%, mean = 3.25), and a strong culture of providing constructive feedback is prevalent (94.0%, mean = 3.31). Respondents also highlighted organizational support for a healthy work-life balance (92.4%, mean = 3.36) and their ability to complete tasks on time (87.9%, mean = 3.15).

Regarding personal productivity, most respondents agreed that they effectively prioritize tasks (89.5%, mean = 3.30) and regularly optimize work processes for efficiency (98.6%, mean = 3.39). The ability to multitask without compromising quality received a slightly lower agreement (90.5%, mean = 3.29). Respondents also noted high agreement on making effective use of resources (95.9%, mean = 3.49) and quickly adapting to new tools and technologies (96.6%, mean = 3.43). Overall, the findings underscore the importance of organizational culture in fostering employee engagement, adaptability, and work efficiency.

Test of the Hypotheses

H₀: Organizational culture has no significant effect on employees’ work efficiency in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria.

The null hypothesis, which states that organizational culture has no significant effect on the work efficiency of employees in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria, was tested using simple linear regression analysis. The values of work efficiency were regressed on the value of organizational culture in the analysis. The data for organizational culture (independent variable) was generated by summing the responses of all the items, whereas work efficiency (dependent variable) was generated by adding the responses of all the items used to measure the variable. The results of the regression test are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of Regression Analysis for the Effect of Organizational Culture on Employees’ Work Efficiency in Selected Polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria

Model		F(df)	ANOVA Sig
R	0.593		
R Square	0.352	235.354 (1,434)	0.000
Adjusted R-square	0.350		
Coefficients	Unstandardized Coefficients	T	Sig
(Constant)	1.685	15.491	.000
Organizational culture	0.501	15.341	.000

- a. Dependent variable: Work efficiency
- b. Predictors: (Constant), organizational culture

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey Results (2024)

Table 3 shows that organizational culture has a positive and statistically significant relationship with the work efficiency of employees in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria (R = 0.593, p<0.05). The coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.352 shows that organizational culture predicts 35.2% of the changes in work efficiency, while the remaining 64.8% changes in the work efficiency of employees in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria are explained by external factors other than those examined in this study. Table 3 shows the results of the ANOVA (overall model significance) of the regression test, which revealed that organizational culture has a

significant effect on the work efficiency of employees in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria. This could be explained by the F-value (235.354) and low p-value (0.000), which is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval. Hence, the result posited that organizational culture within selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria significantly influenced the work efficiency of employees. Moreover, scholars have provided an additional threshold for understanding the values of R^2 . The R^2 values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 for endogenous latent variables can be considered substantial, moderate, and weak, respectively. Hence, with reference to R^2 criterion, it is safe to say that organizational culture has a weak effect on the work efficiency of employees in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria.

Furthermore, the results of the regression coefficients revealed a positive and statistically significant relative influence on organizational culture. Specifically, the results reveal that at 95% confidence level, organizational culture ($\beta = 0.501$, $p = 0.000$, $t = 15.341$) of the employees in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria is statistically significant as the p-values were less than 0.05 and the t-values were greater than 1.96. This shows that a unit change in organizational culture will lead to a 0.501 increase in the work efficiency of employees in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria, given that all other factors are held constant. Based on the path coefficient, the regression model is as follows:

$$\mathbf{WE = 1.685 + 0.501OC \text{ ----- (i)}}$$

WE = Work efficiency

OC = organizational culture

On the strength of this result ($R^2 = 0.352$, $F(1,434) = 235.354$, $p = 0.000$), this study rejects the null hypothesis (H_0), which states that organizational culture has no significant effect on employees' work efficiency in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the simple regression analysis indicate that the organizational culture has a positive and statistically significant impact on the work efficiency of employees in the polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria. This finding is consistent with those of previous empirical studies, which have shown that organizational culture has a positive impact on employee work efficiency. For example, some scholars revealed that a supportive and adaptable corporate culture is positively correlated with employee commitment, motivation, and performance. Employees are more inclined to align with the objectives of the organization, resulting in enhanced productivity and efficiency, when they perceive the organizational culture as fostering innovation, collaboration, and learning (Devonish, 2023). Furthermore, a scholar noted that a robust and unified organizational culture fosters a setting in which employees have a clear understanding of their responsibilities, comprehend the expectations of the organization, and operate with greater efficiency. Numerous studies have emphasized that a favorable organizational culture can cultivate elevated levels of engagement and job satisfaction, thus enhancing efficiency and performance (Strong et al., 2023).

In contrast, several studies have provided contradictory results, indicating that organizational culture does not consistently lead to enhanced employee productivity. Indeed, scholars contended that an inflexible or excessively hierarchical culture may impede employee autonomy and creativity, both of which are essential for effective job performance, in certain instances. Research findings indicate that employees in firms characterized by too formal cultures often encounter diminished levels of innovation and adaptability, compromising work efficiency (Tennin, 2023). Moreover, some scholars discovered that a lack of congruence between the personal values of employees and the culture of the organization can lead to conflict and discontent, ultimately reducing work performance and efficiency. This dissenting perspective emphasizes that the influence of organizational

culture on efficiency is not consistently beneficial and can differ based on the characteristics of the culture and its congruence with employee values (Xaba et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of organizational culture on the work efficiency of employees in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria. Both descriptive and regression analyses were performed. The regression results reveal that one-unit increase in organizational culture (0.501); increases work efficiency by 0.501 units. The t-statistic (15.341) and its highly significant p-value (0.000) confirm that the effect of organizational culture on work efficiency is statistically significant. The analysis deduced that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on the work efficiency of employees in selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria ($R^2=0.352$, $F(1,434) = 235.354$, $p = 0.000$). Based on the empirical findings, this study concluded that there was a statistically significant effect of organizational culture on employee work efficiency. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that organizational culture contributes to employees' work efficiency in the selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria. However, the effect is small, suggesting that more effort is required by the management of the selected polytechnics in Southwest Nigeria to actively promote an inclusive and diverse work culture, have a strong culture of providing constructive feedback within the institution, and support a healthy work-life balance for its employees.

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